

From Historical Legacies to Modern Conflicts: Territorial and Resource Issues in Central Asia

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Abstract

For more than 30 years, the countries of Central Asia - Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan - have adopted a declaration of independence, sharing the same history, cultural heritage and resources. Over the past thirty years, despite the challenges faced by the Central Asian countries, they have become increasingly aware of the importance of their common historical heritage. These nations share a rich history dating back to great empires, such as the Timurid Empire, which has left a deep mark on the culture, architecture and art of the region. It was a time when science, art and trade flourished, with cities like Samarqand and Bukhara becoming centers of cultural exchange and prosperity. Today, these countries embrace this common heritage to strengthen ties with one another. However, it's worth noting that since independence, they have faced a myriad of problems related to the 1920s territorial demarcation that occurred under Soviet rule, including arbitrary border delineations and ethnic divisions that have created ongoing tensions. The borders established during the Soviet period often failed to reflect the demographic and cultural realities of the region, leading to persistent territorial disputes and ethnic strife. Compounding these challenges are critical issues related to resource management, particularly concerning resources, especially water resources, that are essential for economic development and stability. Through a systematic literature review and thematic analysis, this research paper aims to explore the multifaceted nature of conflicts in Central Asia, examining the historical, political, and resource-related dimensions that contribute to inter-state tensions. By examining the historical legacy of the region, on particular the impact of the Soviet period's borders and ethnic divisions, the study seeks to clarify how these factors shape contemporary geopolitical dynamics. The findings will not only deepen our understanding of the complexities associated with these conflicts, but also suggest potential avenues for conflict resolution and regional cooperation. Ultimately, this study is intended to make a valuable contribution to understanding the current challenges and opportunities for enhancing stability in this strategically important region.

Keywords: *Central Asia, Soviet Union, relationships, conflicts, Fergana Valley, territorial disputes, water resources.*

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Introduction

The Timurid Empire, which flourished in the late 14th and early 15th centuries, stands as a significant chapter in the history of Central Asia. Founded by Timur (Tamerlane), this empire extended across vast territories, including present-day Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, and parts of Iran and Afghanistan. The Timurid period was characterized by significant advancements in art, science, architecture, poetry, miniature painting, and literature, and cities such as Samarqand and Bukhara became cultural epicenters. Grandiose architectural designs such as the Registan in Samarqand and the Shah-i-Zinda complex reflect the cultural richness and architectural innovation of the empire. These monuments not only symbolize the might of the empire, but also serve as a testament to the common heritage of the peoples of the region. In addition, the Timurid court attracted scholars, poets, and artists from different countries, which fostered an atmosphere of intellectual exchange. This cultural syncretism helped forge ties between the empire's various ethnic groups, including Uzbeks, Tajiks, and others, creating a sense of shared identity that has persisted through the centuries.

Centuries later, in the 19th century, Russian Empire began to actively expand its possessions in Central Asia, which led to the integration of these lands into the Russian Empire. The conquest of Central Asia by the Russian Empire was a series of military campaigns of the Russian army against Central Asian khanates and ethnic groups in the second half of the XIX century, called Turkestan campaigns or Central Asian campaigns. After the final annexation of Kazakhstan in the 1840s and the liquidation of the Kazakh zhuzes, in the geopolitical context of the “the Great Game”, Russia, after a series of military campaigns against the Khanates of Kokand and Khiva, as well as the Emirate of Bukhara, annexed them. By the 1890s, the annexation of Central Asia (Turkestan) was completed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Russian troops taking Samarqand, June 8, 1868. Karazin N.H.

At the beginning of the 20th century, Central Asia became part of the Soviet Union, where the formation of modern nation-states continued. In the 1920s and 1930s, under Soviet rule, the territorial division of Central Asia changed several times with the Soviet Union republic status of the five now independent states and their current borderlines emerging only in 1936 (Batsaikhan, & Dabrowski, 2017). Once the Soviet Union was dissolved in December 1991, the local political

elites (mostly former leaders of the republican structures of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union) grasped the opportunity and started to establish new regimes (except Kyrgyzstan), based on national rather than communist ideologies. Once on December 25, 1991, the Soviet hammer and sickle flag lowered for the last time over the Kremlin, thereafter replaced by the Russian tricolor, the local political elites (mostly former leaders of the republican structures of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union) grasped the opportunity and started to establish new regimes (except Kyrgyzstan), based on national rather than communist ideologies (Batsaikhan, & Dabrowski, 2017).

With the exception of the Tajik war of the early 1990s, contrary to often voiced fears, Central Asia has been fairly peaceful since independence in 1991 until recently. However, after the dissolution of the Soviet Union, the new states faced a number of challenges, related primarily to the political development of the Central Asian states and the entire region. First of all, many industrial enterprises in Central Asia lost access to their traditional customer bases and suppliers within the former Soviet bloc, and the necessary financial support to maintain and modernize these industries, that led to partial deindustrialization in the post-Soviet period. Secondly, disputes arose, which continue to this day, over access to water, energy, and other resources across borders, and armed clashes, such as Kyrgyz-Uzbek border conflict in 2014 or hostilities between Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan in 2022 year, along disputed portions of the borders were not uncommon. In addition, each country was focused on strengthening its state and national priorities, and the geopolitical position of the region and its resource potential, generated fierce competition and distrust between geopolitical players in the region, reducing the willingness for regional cooperation. Despite all the disputes and difficulties, in recent years the Central Asian countries have managed to make progress in resolving these thorny issues and building regional cooperation schemes. The two states in the region, Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan, which claim leadership in Central Asia, have made significant progress in their economic development.

Contrary to popular perception, Central Asia is currently the most dynamic part of the world (Åslund, 2003), located at the junction of Europe and Asia, which has attracted the close interest of the world's leading powers and international organizations, that include the United States, Russia, China, Turkey, the EU, Iran, India and Japan, which are seeking to expand their political, economic and strategic influence. The main reason is that Central Asia today represents one of the world's last great frontiers for geological survey and analysis, offering opportunities for the discovery, production, transportation, and refining of enormous quantities of oil (10.1 billion barrels of undeveloped proven oil reserves) and gas (6.65 trillion cubic meters (tcm) of natural gas) and other energy resources, that await investments (Dorian, 2006). In this respect, the countries of Central Asia surpass many neighboring states and in general represent a unique storehouse of urgently needed resources for the world.

However, despite their promising potential, there are a number of factors that not only significantly hamper the economic development of the countries of the region, but also become causes of interstate conflicts. The main such factors are:

- a) the borders defined by the Soviet authorities without taking into account the ethnic, historical, and economic peculiarities of the region;
- b) water resources, which have been a stumbling block between the republics since independence;

Literature Review

In recent years, the study of the reasons and consequences of tense relations between the countries of Central Asia has garnered significant attention within the field of international relations. Researchers have increasingly recognized the importance of understanding that the causes of disagreements between the friendly countries of the former Soviet Union stem primarily from the Soviet period, which has left an indelible imprint on their current relations and laid the foundation for their subsequent conflicts.

Dmitrieva (2018) provides overview of post-Soviet Central Asia, highlighting the ethnic-territorial disputes and border conflicts that have emerged since the dissolution of the Soviet Union. She argues that the collapse of the Soviet Union exacerbated existing tensions between ethnic groups, as new state borders often run along historically cohesive communities. Dmitrieva highlights specific cases of conflict resulting from these demarcations, emphasizing that the lack of effective governance and dialogue between states has further complicated the situation. In similar vein, Bochkareva (2019) focuses on the national-territorial demarcation in 1924, investigating its causes and its enduring impact on ethnic-political processes in Central Asia. She argues that the arbitrary borders established during this period did not reflect the demographic realities of the region, leading to significant discontent and conflict. Bochkareva also analyzes the political motivations behind the border delineation, highlighting how Soviet authorities prioritized administrative efficiency over ethnic considerations. In addition, focusing on Kyrgyz-Uzbek border disputes, Zakirova and Zakirov (2022) analyze the post-Soviet period's territorial disagreement. They highlight the recurring nature of these conflicts and their implications for bilateral relations and regional stability. Gamidov and Kurnikin (2023) examine in detail the emergency of border disputes in 1920s, paying more attention to the process of partitioning the territories of Central Asia, especially the Ferghana Valley region, and describing the difficulties and grievances that followed this process.

Water resource conflicts are another critical aspect of inter-state relations in Central Asia. Borisova (2014) explores the historical development of conflicts over water resources in Central Asia during the post-Soviet period. Her article outlines how competing national interests and inadequate cooperation mechanisms have led to tensions surrounding shared water sources. Borisova argues that the legacy of Soviet water management policies, which prioritized irrigation and agricultural productivity, continues to influence current disputes.

In summary, the findings from this review indicate that effective conflict resolution in Central Asia requires a multi-faceted approach that acknowledge historical injustices, addresses contemporary grievances, and fosters regional cooperation.

Methodology

This research paper discusses the main points of convergence between the interests of Central Asian countries, which are ultimately the causes of conflict and tension, focusing more on the situation in Uzbekistan. It also employs a qualitative methodology, emphasizing the historical, political, and resource-related factors that contribute to these dynamics. The analysis incorporates a systematic review of existing literature, including studies on ethnical-territorial disputes and water resource conflicts. It was identified around 50 key articles that highlight the legacies of Soviet period's border delineations and their ongoing impact on ethnic tensions, especially in the works of Dmitrieva and Bochkareva.

In order to collect data, it was utilized academic databases such as Google Scholar and institutional repositories to identify pertinent literature. It was developed my own search strategy to retrieve a broad spectrum of relevant studies. To achieve this, there was created a list of keywords and phrases

relates to the topic, such as “Central Asia conflicts”, “ethnic disputes”, “border conflicts”, “water resource management”, “post-Soviet dynamics”, and “Ferghana Valley”. Articles were included if they addressed relationships specifically among Central Asian countries, consisted of empirical studies, theoretical frameworks, or policy analyses, and were published within the last 10-15 years. Conversely, articles published in languages other than English or Russian were not considered, as this could limit accessibility and the ability to analyze findings effectively. Once the literature was collected, thematic analysis was used to analyze the data systematically. The selected articles were read and re-read to gain a comprehensive understanding of their content. Contextual interpretation was then engaged in, where was interpreted the themes within the broader socio-political and historical context of Central Asia. At the end of this research, it was concluded that the arbitrary borders established during the Soviet period have not only fragmented ethnic groups, but have also created enduring tensions and territorial disputes.

Discussion

Legacy of Soviet administrative-territorial division. Since independence, ethno-territorial conflicts between the Central Asian republics of the former Soviet Union have become more prominent, and border areas are experiencing increasing tension, as the borders established during the Soviet period, which in the past had a formal character within the framework of a single state, today no longer suit the newly independent states (Dmitrieva, 2018). Throughout the entire period of the USSR, certain territories within what are now the Central Asian republics were frequently reassigned between republics. The borders were altered, and some areas were temporarily allocated to neighboring republics in an attempt to resolve land use issues, but these actions ultimately exacerbated conflicts in the long term. According to the results of the Central Asian Agency for Policy Research (ARR), the issue of disputed territories was ranked first in the rating of existing interstate problems in Central Asia (Dmitrieva, 2018).

Speaking about the Soviet partition of Central Asia, it should be noted that one of the key events that had a lasting impact on the current geopolitical situation in Central Asia was the process called “National Delimitation” that took place in the region in 1924-1925. Its goals were, on the one hand, to create the appearance of national autonomy and, on the other hand, to maintain control over the region and govern it through the new national Soviet structures.

Before the 1917 revolution, the Turkestan Governor-General's Office, the Bukhara Emirate and the Khanate of Khiva existed in Central Asia. After the establishment of Soviet power in 1920-1921, the Turkestan ASSR (Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic), the Bukharan People's Soviet Republic and the Khorezm People's Soviet Republic were formed on these lands.

Subsequent events and territorial changes occurred rather quickly, and it took time to consolidate the new territorial-administrative structure in the region. The first step was the formation on October 27, 1924 of the Turkmen SSR and the Uzbek SSR with a formal and conventional capital in Bukhara on the basis of the former Bukhara and Khorezm republics. These new union republics were to correspond to the predominant settlement of Turkmens and Uzbeks. The Turkmen SSR encompassed the Krasnovodsk, Merv, Poltoratsy and Tedzhen districts of the Turkmen region, as well as the Turkmen Autonomous Oblast from the Bukhara People's Soviet Republic and the Turkmen Autonomous Oblast from the Khorezm People's Soviet Republic. The Uzbek SSR included the territories of most of Bukhara SSR, Khorezm SSR, as well as Samarkand region, most of the Fergana region and Tashkent uyezd of Syrdarya region of the Turkestan ASSR. At the same time, the Tajik ASSR was formed in the southern part of the Uzbek SSR.

In April 1929, the II Congress of Soviets of the Tajik ASSR was held, the most important act of which was the decision to incorporate the Khojent district of the Uzbek SSR, populated predominantly by Tajiks, into the Tajik ASSR, thus completing the process of unification of the Tajik lands into a single national state (Toshev, 2014). On October 16, 1929, the III Extraordinary Congress of Soviets of the USSR ratified the Declaration converting the Tajik ASSR into the Tajik SSR. The new republic incorporated the Autonomous Oblast of Gorno-Bakhshan, as well as the district of Garm, Hissar, Kulyab, Kurgan-Tyubinsk, Penjikent, and the Ura-Tyubinsk, along with the Khodjent district, which was transferred from the Uzbek SSR. Eventually, on December 5, 1929, the Tajik SSR was formed.

However, it is worth noting that the Tajiks did not demand the creation of “their own state” when partitioning to create their own national states: the Bukhara, Khorezm and Turkestan republics (Beyssembiev, 2013). Thus, Stalin in a conversation with B.G. Gafurov, a Soviet statesman and party figure and historian and orientalist, emphasized: “The formation of the Tajik SSR in 1924 was not desired first of all by the Tajiks themselves and they prevented it as much as possible” (Beyssembiev, 2013).

Moreover, as a result of the national-state partitioning of Central Asia in 1924-1925, practically all the territories where the Kazakh population prevailed were united in a single Kazakh autonomy, and in February 1925 the Orenburg region was withdrawn from the Kirghiz ASSR and transferred to the direct subordination of the RSFSR. The Kirghiz ASSR also included the Syrdarya and Jetysu regions of the former Turkestan ASSR with Kazakh population and the Karakalpak Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic, and the Orenburg region together with the capital Orenburg were returned to the direct subordination of the RSFSR. Later, in June 1925, the Kyrgyz ASSR, which acquired new borders, by the Decree of the All-Union Central Executive Committee received a new name Kazak Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic, which was due to the change of the Russian name of the Kazakh ethnos, which received the official spelling “Cossacks”.

On July 20, 1930, the Karakalpak Autonomous Region was transferred from the Kazak ASSR to the direct subordination of the RSFSR, which later in 1936 was transferred to the Uzbek SSR and transformed into the Karakalpak ASSR. In 1932, the entire territory along the Kara-Bogaz-Gol Bay, which had previously been part of the Kazakh ASSR, was transferred to the Turkmen SSR. In December 1934, the territory in the northwest of the republic was transferred to the newly formed Orenburg Region. In February 1936, the Russian spelling of the name of the Kazakh ethnos was changed again - instead of the former “Kazakhs” the modern spelling “Kazakhs” was adopted, respectively, the Kazakh ASSR was renamed the Kazakh ASSR, and on December 5, 1936, with the adoption of the new Constitution of the USSR, the status of the Kazakh ASSR was raised to a union republic, respectively, it was withdrawn from the RSFSR and transformed into the Kazakh Soviet Socialist Republic.

It should be noted that the Kyrgyz ASSR, which existed in 1920-1925 mainly on the territory of present-day Kazakhstan, should not be confused with the Kyrgyz ASSR, which existed in 1926-1936 mainly on the territory of present-day Kyrgyzstan. Before the revolution, Kazakhs in Russia were called Kirghiz or Kirghiz-Kaisaks, and Kyrgyz were called Kara-Kirghiz; this tradition existed in the early years of Soviet power, so the republic was originally called the Kirghiz ASSR (while the Kirghiz autonomy was called Kara-Kirghiz until May 1925) (International Communications, 2020).

The task of creating an independent autonomy of the Kyrgyz within the Turkestan ASSR has been raised since 1921. Only on October 14, 1924 at the session of the All-Russian Central Executive Committee of the USSR the resolution of the All-Russian Central Executive Committee on the formation of the Kara-Kyrgyz Autonomous Oblast within the RSFSR was adopted. Due to the fact that the Constituent Congress of Soviets proposed to omit the offensive-sounding prefix

“Kara”, which meant “black”, the All-Russian Central Executive Committee of the RSFSR renamed the Kara-Kirghiz AO into the Kirghiz Autonomous Oblast by its resolution of May 25, 1925 (Usegenov, 2010). Based on the principle of self-determination of peoples and the will of the Kyrgyz people, in order to provide the workers of Kirghizia with greater opportunities for the manifestation of labor initiative and self-activity in socialist construction, the Presidium of the All-Russian Central Executive Committee on February 1, 1926 decided to transform the Kirghiz Autonomous Oblast into the Kirghiz ASSR (Usegenov, 2010). The XIII All-Russian Congress of Soviets on April 15, 1927 finally legalized the formation of the Kirghiz ASSR (Usegenov, 2010). And already on December 5, 1936 the Kirghiz ASSR was transformed into the Kirghiz SSR, thus completing the process of separation and formation of national republics in Central Asia.

Despite Moscow's mediation efforts, practically all the union and autonomous republics of Central Asia were not satisfied with the border line. In deciding the question of assigning certain territories of Central Asia to the new national republics, the subcommissions in their work should be based on the following principles: the national composition of the majority of the population of the territory in question; the unity of the territories of the new national units so that they would not be interspersed with each other (Bochkareva, 2019). However, in most cases, the demarcation was seen by local national elites as an opportunity to expand the territory of their national republic, which often led to territorial disputes.

The main justification for territorial claims was the ethnicity of the population of this or that territory, so that there was no talk of pan-Turkic unity. For instance, the territorial ambitions of the Kazakh side encompassed not only the lands of the Syr-Darya and Jetysu (formerly Semirechenka) provinces of the Turkic Republic, but also to the Amu-Darya province, Tashkent and Mirzachul districts, as well as the regions in Fergana and Pamir, where the Kazakhs and related groups such as the Kara-Kirghiz, Karakalpaks, and Kipchaks made up the majority of the population. The claims of the Kazakh side to several volosts of the Tashkent district were rejected for economic reasons, as their transfer to the Kazakh SSR would have violated the unity of administrative control and economic management of the irrigation system providing water to Tashkent (Bochkareva, 2019).

P. Masov, referring to attempts to include Tajiks into the Turkic people (the influence of pan-Turkism), machinations in the census process comes to the conclusion about the “axe division” of Central Asia by the Soviet leadership (Khamidov, & Kurnykin, 2023). The Bolsheviks understood the unequal economic potential and level of development of the created national republics and therefore tried in some cases to level this difference by assigning to one or another national unit urban centers that could act as a pole of growth for the rural district. As an example, the city of Osh in the Fergana Valley, where the Uzbek population predominated, was transferred to the Kara-Kirghiz Autonomous District.

At the same time, the existing socio-economic complexes were not always taken into account, such as the territory of the Fergana Valley, which was divided between the Uzbek SSR, the Tajik ASSR within it and the Kara-Kirghiz ASSR within the RSFSR (Osh), and the lands adjacent to the oasis from the north were transferred to the Kazakh ASSR (Chimkent, Aulie-Ata), despite the fact that it was populated predominantly by Uzbeks. The main reason why attention should be paid to the administrative-territorial demarcation in one of the most important regions of Central Asia, the Ferghana Valley (Ferghana Oblast and a small part of Samarkand Oblast), is that from the very beginning the boundaries established here became a sore point in Soviet Central Asia and the cause of many conflicts and disputes between Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan and Tajikistan that continue to this day. The Soviet policy of partition officially created the current administrative-state boundaries in Central Asia, with some disputed parts of the borders of Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan and Tajikistan in the Ferghana Valley (figure 2.). In particular, the inter-republican borders in the Ferghana Valley

are perceived by many experts as an artificial structure built specifically to sustain long-term conflicts, as a realization of the “divide and rule” strategy, or simply as the result of incompetent governance (Khamidov, & Kurnykin, 2023).

The Economist

Figure 2. The map of Fergana Valley

Inter-ethnic strife became a mass character in the late Soviet Union, turning almost into a pattern. One vivid example of armed conflict between the countries of Central Asia can serve as the event of June 7, 1990, the climax of the clash between Kyrgyz and Uzbeks in the city of Osh. Throughout the spring of 1990, there were almost continuous rallies of Kyrgyz youth demanding land in the Kyrgyz capital, and attempts to squat land plots continued unabated. To suppress the unrest, the Soviet authorities had to introduce army units into the emergency zone. “At the cost of enormous efforts of the army and militia, it was possible to avoid the involvement of the Uzbek population in the conflict on the territory of the Kyrgyz SSR. The march of armed Uzbeks from the cities of Namangan and Andijan to Osh was stopped several dozen kilometers from the city. Cases of clashes with army units were recorded. Then the main political and religious figures of the Uzbek SSR addressed the Uzbeks rushing to Kyrgyzstan, which helped to avoid further casualties,” historian Mikhail Zhironkhov stated in his book “Seeds of Disintegration: Wars and Conflicts on the Territory of the Former USSR” (Okunev, 2020). If unofficial sources are to be believed, the number of victims of the clashes in Osh oblast was in the thousands - and could be as high as 10,000 people (Okunev, 2020).

Long-standing disputes between Kyrgyz and Uzbeks over land escalated again in January 2010, when Osh Mayor Melisbek Myrzakmatov announced his intention to develop a master plan for

the reconstruction of the city. On June 10-15 of the same year, new inter-ethnic clashes took place, resulting in numerous casualties. The first clash between groups of Kyrgyz and Uzbek youths occurred near a casino in the center of Osh on the night of June 10-11 (Belyalova, 2015). The unrest quickly engulfed the entire city and began to spread beyond its borders. On June 12, the unrest spread to neighboring Jalalabad province, leading to killings, fights and pogroms that lasted for several days (Belyalova, 2015). According to official data, as a result of the riots, more than 400 people were killed, about 2 thousand people were wounded and injured (according to unofficial data, more than 2 thousand people were killed), and material damage amounted to about 80 million dollars (Belyalova, 2015). 6,000 tons of humanitarian aid from a number of states and international organizations, including Russia, were sent to the affected regions of Kyrgyzstan (Belyalova, 2015). On July 27, 2010, international donor organizations decided to allocate \$1.1 billion to Kyrgyzstan (Belyalova, 2015).

In both cases cited above, the initial response of both the Kyrgyz and Uzbek governments was swift and decisive. Recognizing the gravity of the situation, the Kyrgyz authorities declared a state of emergency in Osh. The sight of soldiers on the streets served both as a deterrent to potential insurgents and as a signal that the government would not tolerate ethnic violence. In addition to military intervention, the authorities imposed a curfew and restrictions on movement around the city. By limiting the hours that people could be on the streets, the government sought to minimize the potential for further conflict by demonstrating its commitment to restoring peace, and to provide security for residents of both ethnic groups. Realizing that military measures could not solve the problem in the long term, the authorities also initiated dialogue. They facilitated discussions between Kyrgyz and Uzbek community leaders. In addition, the authorities launched investigations or participated in the clashes. This approach was aimed not only at obtaining justice for the victims, but also at demonstrating that governments were serious about upholding the law. By ensuring that perpetrators were punished, the authorities hoped to prevent future violence and restore public confidence in their authority.

Additional complications in interstate relations in the region are brought by enclaves: Uzbek enclaves (Sokh, Shakhimardan) on the territory of Kyrgyzstan, Tajik enclaves on the territory of Uzbekistan (Sarvak) and Kyrgyzstan (Vorukh). The tense situation on the borders has repeatedly led to various incidents - road blockades, mass fights and situations on the brink of war. Conflicts have erupted either over access to water or pasture, or in protest against overly strict border crossing regimes. Bans and restrictions on the use of roads through the enclaves, which connect the surrounding settlements, have also contributed to tensions. The issue is further aggravated by the fact that new oil fields have been discovered in Sokha. Uzbekistan, which has a more powerful military, is taking advantage of this by building up its military contingent on the borders with Kyrgyzstan and in the Sokh enclave (Vasiliev, 2012). The resolution of borders among Central Asian states is complicated by Soviet period's documents and maps that depict varying boundaries of the Fergana Valley, as its territory was redefined multiple times during the 1920s, 1950s, and 1980s. At the same time, each state, in its efforts to resolve territorial disputes, tends to utilize documents that support its position and provide it with an advantage.

Only after Sh. Mirziyoyev came to power in Uzbekistan has there been a breakthrough in the settlement of territorial disputes. This is evidenced by the signing in 2017 of an agreement to harmonize 1,170 (out of 1,380) km of the Kyrgyz-Uzbek border, which is a great achievement in solving border problems (Zakirova, & Zakirov, 2022). Strategic sites such as the Kempir-Abad reservoir, the Gavasay site in Jalal-Abad province, the area around the Sokh enclave in Batken province and some others remained disputed (Zakirova, & Zakirov, 2022).

Some scholars argue that a constructive approach to addressing regional border and territorial issues could involve establishing an agreement regarding the international legal status of enclaves

in Central Asia. Moreover, unlike a simple border delimitation agreement, this document should encompass a comprehensive range of issues related to the livelihoods of border security, and the deployment of military units.

Water resources. With the collapse of the USSR and the acquisition of national sovereignty by the Central Asian republics, the outdated regional water and energy division system began to unravel, and water consumption increased sharply and reached a level that became impossible to maintain. This is due to population and demand growth, but still, it does not constitute the main share in water consumption. Agriculture, energy and industry take a significant part in the consumption. Irrigation systems have deteriorated to the point where nearly half of all water fails to reach the fields. Additionally, several years of low water levels have diminished available water resources by one-fifth, while the demand for water continues to rise steadily. In the Soviet Union, water and energy resources were exchanged freely throughout its territory, crossing only the administrative boundaries of the republics, with Moscow providing funds and managing the construction and maintenance of infrastructure (International Crisis Group, 2002). The growing mutual dissatisfaction among the states, no longer held in check by any regulatory framework, began to manifest as breaches of mutual obligations and the emergency of new demands.

For example, in 2001, although water from the Toktogul reservoir in Kyrgyzstan was released in the agreed-upon volume, the summer electricity consumption by Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan was lower than what had been stipulated in the contract. Consequently, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan were forced to switch their hydroelectric power plants from irrigation to energy production, releasing all accumulated water during the colder months to ensure that their own populations had heat and light. This decision ultimately resulted in flooding in the territories of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan.

Realizing that their main resource is water, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, with the support of World Bank experts, insisted on payment for their water storage and supply services, arguing that water is also a commodity, while the “lower” countries insisted that “water is a common good and an asset to which access cannot be restricted” (Borisova, E. (2014)). Thus, the lack of a common water policy and the gradual abandonment of the old model increasingly entangled the tangle of contradictions. The latent conflict over water and energy resources has grown so much with associated problems that the countries of the region do not consider it possible to unravel this tangle by returning to the Soviet, even if modernized, model of management (Borisova, E. (2014)).

Every year, disputes arise between two groups of countries: the three downstream countries - Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and Uzbekistan, which consume huge amounts of water for cotton cultivation, and the upstream countries - Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan (Borisova, E. (2014)). Downstream countries require increasing amounts of water to support their expanding agricultural sectors and growing populations, while economically weaker upstream countries seek greater control over their resources, aiming to utilize more water for power generation and agricultural development. As a result, this leads to the fact that the countries not only accuse each other of excessive water consumption, but also do it to the detriment of their neighbors. Thus, Turkmenistan consumes too much water to the detriment of Uzbekistan, which in turn is accused by Kazakhstan of consuming more water than the norm, and Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan in turn claim that all three downstream countries exceed quotas (International Crisis Group, 2002). Currently, countries rely more on their internal resources and the support of external sponsors, which has unfortunately led to a significant reduction in the scope and limitation of voluntary cooperation between countries.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Central Asia's complex geopolitical landscape is shaped by a combination of historical legacies, territorial disputes and an urgent need for effective resource management. As the region continues to recover from the collapse of the Soviet Union, relations between Central Asian countries are increasingly marred by competing national interests and unresolved conflicts over both territory and water resources.

This study emphasizes that territorial disputes in Central Asia are deeply intertwined with issues of identity, historical grievances, and resource distribution. Arbitrary borders established during the Soviet period have led to ongoing tensions as countries vie for control over strategically important areas such as the Ferghana Valley. At the same time, disputes between upstream and downstream countries over water use further complicate these relationships as agricultural and energy needs collide.

An agreement that addresses not only border demarcation but also equitable management of shared resources is needed to enhance regional stability. A cooperative framework that promotes dialogue and cooperation is critical to easing tensions and resolving disputes.

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